

Linear Estimation of Network Specificity (LENS) for Identification of Speech- vs. Noise-Selective Filters in Deep Speech Enhancement

Eike J. Nustede, Jörn Anemüller

Dept. of Medical Physics and Acoustics, Carl von Ossietzky University Oldenburg, Germany

Abstract

Understanding functional processing within deep speech enhancement models remains a challenge, particularly in characterizing how specific filters respond to different signal compositions. We propose an interpretability analysis framework, built on a linear decomposition of feature maps into clean speech and noise contributions, for a U-Net-based speech enhancement model. Using derived scaling coefficients for speech and noise, ψ and η , respectively, the method directly quantifies the relative contributions of both signal components. To summarize filter behavior across the network, we introduce the pseudo-SNR (pSNR), a log-scaled ratio of ψ to η that serves as a compact proxy for signal composition within feature activations. Based on these coefficients, we classify filters across the U-Net's layers as speech-, noise-, and non-specific, and analyze their roles in processing individual utterances, revealing trends in signal selectivity throughout the encoding-decoding cycle.

Results show that speech-specific filters predominate across almost all layers, while noise-specific filters are relatively rare. Moreover, pSNR values in speech-specific filters tend to increase toward deeper network layers. Notably, this speech-specificity is not static: Filters adapt dynamically on a per-utterance basis rather than exhibiting fixed selectivity averaged across the dataset. This finding indicates that, while our framework relies on a linearity assumption, it remains well-suited for analyzing non-linear deep networks by decomposing overall processing through layer- and utterance-specific linear approximations. Overall, our approach offers a principled method to interpret and compare deep speech enhancement models based on internal activation behavior, with potential to guide architectural improvements.

Keywords: Speech enhancement, Deep Neural Network Interpretability, U-Net, Feature decomposition, Filter classification, Signal selectivity

1. Introduction

Interest in explainable AI (XAI) has been rising since deep neural networks (DNNs) have been applied to a plethora of applications. In the audio processing domain, DNNs are employed in a variety of tasks including, e.g., classification (acoustic scenes, speakers or noise sources), source separation (speakers, musical instruments and singers, speech and noise) and audio reconstruction (speech enhancement, anomaly detection). However, interpretability of DNNs in audio processing problems remains a challenging task, arguably more so than in computer vision, largely due to the difficulty associated with interpreting the features that are used in audio tasks. Spectrogram data and more so waveform audio, during processing in a network, unlike images often elude interpretations by human observers because the spectral and temporal structures of audio signals, while rich in information, lack an intuitive, visual correspondence like the edges or textures found in natural images. Superimpositions of more than one audio source make identification and assignment of typical audio characteristics like onset, harmonics or formant not only harder to identify but

also difficult to allocate to either of the constituent sources. Thus, many algorithms that have been successfully used in, e.g., the field of computer vision prove less straightforward in their application to the analysis of audio networks. This challenge precludes the audio field from several network interpretability approaches that otherwise might be instrumental in advancements with respect to, e.g., model debugging, trustworthiness, and the development of novel architectures tailored to audio processing.

Among the different approaches to network interpretability that have been proposed, most model-specific approaches are based on evaluating gradient information and the backpropagation mechanism to determine the importance of features contained in the input by following the gradient. For example, the integrated gradients method [1] calculates feature importance by integrating gradients of the model's output with respect to the input along a path from a baseline to the actual input. Other notable methods include, e.g., guided backpropagation [2], saliency maps [3], and GradCAM [4]. Gradient-based approaches often produce images with little resemblance to natural images, hence being hard to interpret. Several regu-

larization methods were introduced to improve these images, e.g., by focusing on the features of specific layers with respect to a certain class [5]. Layer-wise relevance propagation (LRP) [6] is a technique used to explain a network’s decision in classification tasks. It assigns relevance scores to the input features in relation to the network’s output, thereby identifying the inputs’ key features. DeepLIFT [7] is similar to LRP and integrated gradients, as it works by propagating relevance scores layer by layer by comparing a neuron’s activation compared to a reference baseline activation. Another popular approach, activation maximization, is used to generate one input that maximizes the activation of one specific filter kernel [8], thus generating images that should be proportional to the filter itself. Model-agnostic methods include LIME [9], which approximates model predictions by using locally trained interpretable models (e.g., linear regression). LIME perturbs the input and observes, and scores, the changes in output to estimate feature importance. Another popular method is based on game theory. Shapely additive explanations (SHAP) [10] assigns importance scores to features by averaging their marginal contributions across all possible feature combinations.

Audio data in its spectral representation is largely different from natural images, making approaches from computer vision less amenable. Moreover, previous work mostly focused on classification and recognition tasks, where the contribution of different parts of the input to a specific output can be determined. For example, LRP has recently been applied to speaker identification tasks [11]. LIME has been adapted to source separation tasks in audioLIME [12]. Another approach estimates the time-frequency filter mask as a target for SHAP [13] in the context of speech enhancement, but due to the high computational costs, some simplifications must be applied. More recent studies have proposed novel frameworks tailored to the audio domain: Relevance-weights representations have been introduced to improve the interpretability of deep models for speech [14], while interpretable filters in Wav-UNet architectures have shown promise in enhancing transparency in speech enhancement pipelines [15]. Another promising direction lies in unsupervised, interpretable representation learning, e.g., in music source separation tasks [16]. In addition, deep learning systems used in attention decoding through EEG-informed speech separation have been compared to linear models for interpretability [17].

The method reported here, linear estimation of network specificity (LENS), takes the approach of directly analyzing intermediate feature maps in a speech enhancement network. We exploit an approximately linear mixture property of noisy signals, expressed as $\mathbf{X} = \psi \mathbf{S} + \eta \mathbf{N} + \mathcal{E}$, where the learned representations at a given network layer are denoted by \mathbf{S} for a clean speech input, \mathbf{N} for a noise-only input, and \mathbf{X}

for the representation resulting from the corresponding speech-in-noise input. After probing the network with clean, noise-only, and mixed inputs, resulting feature maps are compared using a least-squares estimation of the mixing coefficients ψ and η , applied to each unit independently across all network layers. This permits quantification of relative encoding of speech and noise information at the feature map level. A derived pseudo signal-to-noise ratio (pSNR) in the representation space provides a principled measure of speech or noise sensitivity for individual filters. For reference, we also report cosine similarity between corresponding feature maps, a baseline measure commonly used in related work. Overall, our approach offers a complementary perspective on the internal processing of speech and noise in deep speech enhancement networks.

2. Methods

The following sections outline the methodological approach of this work. Section 2.1 describes the CVU-Net architecture for deep speech enhancement, which, while not the sole applicable domain, serves as the primary application context for the presented analyses. Section 2.2 introduces the proposed linear estimation algorithm for network specificity, followed by a cosine similarity-based method used for comparative evaluation (Section 2.4).

2.1. Variational U-Net architecture

The complex variational U-Net, CVU-Net [18], as illustrated in Fig. 1 and Tab. 1, extends the standard U-Net with a probabilistic latent space akin to the latent space model employed in variational autoencoders (VAEs). Network inputs are formed by log-scaled magnitude spectra and phase information, shown on the left side of the figure. These inputs are fed through a series of downsampling convolutional layers (E1–E4), which include dilated convolutions to increase the receptive field. As typical for U-Nets, the spatial resolution is progressively reduced while the number of feature maps increases, up to a certain point. The subsequent layers (EC1–EC3) preserve the number of feature maps while continuing spatial compression. Note that all convolutions in the network are complex convolutions [19], where each convolutional block in the encoder applies a 3×3 dilated convolution combined with depthwise separable convolutions [20]. The initial dilation rate is set at a receptive field size of 16, which is halved at each subsequent layer, thus adapting to the decreasing size of the feature maps. After the convolution, batch normalization is applied, followed by a parametric ReLU (PReLU) activation. The resulting feature map is split: one part is retained for the U-Net’s lateral skip connection, while the other undergoes max-pooling to downsample both the temporal and spatial dimensions by a factor of two.

Figure 1: Complex-valued variational U-Net architecture (CVU-Net). Left: Input spectrogram with log-scaled magnitude and phase (phase not shown). Center: Encoder (green), probabilistic latent space (gray), lateral skip connections, decoder (orange). Right: Output spectrogram with log-scaled magnitude and phase (phase not shown).

The encoder output is projected into a probabilistic latent space through a 1×1 convolution followed by a PReLU activation (L1). This representation is then passed through two parallel linear layers (L2) that estimate mean and variance of the underlying latent space normal distributions. Samples are drawn from these distributions using the reparameterization trick. The sampled latent representation is passed through an additional feed-forward layer, followed by 1×1 convolution with PReLU activation (L3) before reaching the decoder.

In the decoder, the data is progressively upsampled via transposed convolutions, beginning with DC1-DC3, which maintain the number of channels. At each stage, lateral skip connections fuse features from the corresponding encoder layers to preserve spatial details, with the transposed convolution increasing temporal and spectral dimensions to match those of the lateral connection. The lateral feature maps are then concatenated along the channel axis, effectively doubling the number of feature maps. This expanded representation is subsequently reduced through two convolutional layers, each followed by batch normalization and PReLU activation (D1-D4). The convolutional layers use dilated convolutions, mirroring the dilation used in the encoder. A final 1×1 convolutional layer (O) reduces the number of feature maps from 64 to 2, producing the output spectrum with log-scaled magnitude and a phase. The network with parameters θ , input \mathbf{X} and target output \mathbf{S} is trained with the combined loss function:

$$\mathcal{L}(\theta; \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{S}) = \mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{SI-SDR}} + \mathcal{L}_{\text{MAG}} + \beta \mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}}. \quad (1)$$

The first three terms in 1 are comprised of squared magnitude, squared complex and time-domain SI-SDR loss [18] as

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{MAG}}(\theta; \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{S}) = \|\hat{\mathbf{S}}^{\text{mag}} - \mathbf{S}^{\text{mag}}\|_F^2, \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{MSE}}(\theta; \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{S}) = \|\hat{\mathbf{S}}^{\Re} - \mathbf{S}^{\Re}\|_F^2 + \|\hat{\mathbf{S}}^{\Im} - \mathbf{S}^{\Im}\|_F^2, \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{SI-SDR}}(\theta; \mathbf{x}, \mathbf{s}) = -10 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\|\hat{\mathbf{s}}^T \mathbf{s}\|_2^2}{\|\hat{\mathbf{s}}\|_2^2 \|\mathbf{s}\|_2^2} \right). \quad (4)$$

Here, \mathbf{S}^{mag} and $\hat{\mathbf{S}}^{\text{mag}}$ are the log-scaled magnitude spectra of target \mathbf{S} and network output $\hat{\mathbf{S}}$. Real and

imaginary parts of the complex-valued target and output spectrograms are denoted by \mathbf{S}^{\Re} , \mathbf{S}^{\Im} , $\hat{\mathbf{S}}^{\Re}$ and $\hat{\mathbf{S}}^{\Im}$, respectively. The corresponding time-domain waveform signals of the SI-SDR loss are denoted by \mathbf{s} , \mathbf{x} and $\hat{\mathbf{s}}$, Frobenius norm by $\|\cdot\|_F$.

Under a unit Gaussian prior on the latent variables, the KL regularizer used in (1) becomes

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{KL}} = \frac{1}{2} \|\boldsymbol{\mu}^2 + \boldsymbol{\sigma}^2 - \mathbf{1} - \log \boldsymbol{\sigma}^2\|_1, \quad (5)$$

where the expression is applied to the latent dimensions. The term \mathcal{L}_{KL} is then scaled by a weighting factor β [21].

To allow stochastic latent representations during training, the encoder predicts a mean vector $\boldsymbol{\mu}$ and a log-variance vector $\log \boldsymbol{\sigma}^2$. A latent sample is then obtained via the reparameterization trick

$$\mathbf{z} = \boldsymbol{\mu} + \boldsymbol{\sigma} \odot \boldsymbol{\epsilon}, \quad \boldsymbol{\epsilon} \sim \mathcal{N}(\mathbf{0}, \mathbf{I}), \quad (6)$$

which makes the sampling operation differentiable with respect to the encoder parameters.

2.2. Linear estimation of network specificity (LENS)

Analysis of acoustic signal representations with the LENS (linear estimation of network specificity) method examines feature maps in specific layers of a deep convolutional neural network model. The feature map of a specific network unit within a layer is obtained by recording the activation output from the the corresponding filter kernel in response to a given input and can be visualized as higher-layer feature map [8]. Let \mathbf{X} denote an arbitrary input spectrogram and θ network parameters. The activation of channel k of layer ℓ as a function of input and network parameters is denoted as $\mathbf{X}_{\ell,k} = \mathcal{F}(\mathbf{X}; \theta, \ell, k)$. Each feature map $\mathbf{X}_{\ell,k}$ is a two-dimensional matrix of size $H^{(\ell)} \times W^{(\ell)}$ with activations normalized to the range $[-1, 1]$.

The proposed LENS method aims to quantify the relative contribution of speech and noise components to higher-layer representations within a speech enhancement network. The method operates directly on feature maps extracted from network layers and provides a source-specific characterization at the level

Layer	Operation	Dimension (layer output)
E1	dilated 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU, max-pool	$64 \times 128 \times 128$
E2	dilated 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU, max-pool	$128 \times 64 \times 64$
E3	dilated 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU, max-pool	$256 \times 32 \times 32$
E4	dilated 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU, max-pool	$512 \times 16 \times 16$
EC1	depthwise-separable 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU, max-pool	$512 \times 8 \times 8$
EC2	depthwise-separable 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU, max-pool	$512 \times 4 \times 4$
EC3	depthwise-separable 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU, max-pool	$512 \times 2 \times 2$
L1	1×1 conv., BN, PReLU, flatten	1×2048
L2	Two fc-layers	1×1024
L3	Two fc-layers, unflatten, 1×1 conv., BN, PReLU	$512 \times 2 \times 2$
DC1	3×3 transp. conv., two 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU	$512 \times 4 \times 4$
DC2	3×3 transp. conv., two 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU	$512 \times 8 \times 8$
DC3	3×3 transp. conv., two 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU	$512 \times 16 \times 16$
D1	dilated 3×3 transp. conv., two 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU	$512 \times 32 \times 32$
D2	dilated 3×3 transp. conv., two 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU	$256 \times 64 \times 64$
D3	dilated 3×3 transp. conv., two 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU	$128 \times 128 \times 128$
D4	dilated 3×3 transp. conv., two 3×3 conv., BN, PReLU	$64 \times 256 \times 256$
O	1×1 conv., BN, PReLU	$2 \times 256 \times 256$
Input	complex-valued spectrogram	$2 \times 256 \times 256$
Output	complex-valued spectrogram	$2 \times 256 \times 256$

Table 1: List of layers in the CVU-Net with transforms and output dimensions. BN refers to batch normalization, and PReLU [22] denotes the Parametric Rectified Linear Unit.

Algorithm 1 Linear Estimation of Network Specificity (LENS)

Input: Trained network \mathcal{F} ; paired signals $(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{N}, \mathbf{X})$

Output: Per utterance weights $\psi_{\ell,k}$ and $\eta_{\ell,k}$ for all layers ℓ and channels k

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1: for each utterance triple  $(\mathbf{S}, \mathbf{N}, \mathbf{X})$  do
2:   Extract all  $\mathbf{S}_{\ell,k}$  by forward pass of  $\mathbf{S}$ 
3:   Extract all  $\mathbf{N}_{\ell,k}$  by forward pass of  $\mathbf{N}$ 
4:   Extract all  $\mathbf{X}_{\ell,k}$  by forward pass of  $\mathbf{X}$ 
5:   for each layer  $\ell$  do
6:     for each channel  $k$  in layer  $\ell$  do
7:       Estimate  $(\psi_{\ell,k}, \eta_{\ell,k})$  via constrained LS:

$$(\psi_{\ell,k}, \eta_{\ell,k}) = \arg \min_{\psi, \eta} \|\psi \mathbf{S}_{\ell,k} + \eta \mathbf{N}_{\ell,k} - \mathbf{X}_{\ell,k}\|_F^2$$

       subject to  $0 \leq \psi \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq \eta \leq 1$ 
8:     end for
9:   end for
10: end for

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of individual filters. Rather than relying on similarity measures computed between feature maps, LENS models the feature representation of a speech-in-noise signal as a predominantly linear combination of corresponding clean speech and noise representations. This approach enables a direct estimation of source contributions within the learned representation space and facilitates a layer- and filter-level analysis of speech and noise encoding.

Let $\mathbf{X}_{\ell,k}$ denote the feature map at channel k in

layer ℓ obtained from a mixed signal input that contains speech in noise, feature map $\mathbf{S}_{\ell,k}$ denote the representation obtained from the corresponding speech-only input, and $\mathbf{N}_{\ell,k}$ the representation from the corresponding noise-only input. Our assumption is that the matrices are related through an approximately additive superposition

$$\mathbf{X}_{\ell,k} = \psi \mathbf{S}_{\ell,k} + \eta \mathbf{N}_{\ell,k} + \mathcal{E} \quad (7)$$

with a residual approximation error matrix \mathcal{E} and coefficients ψ and η . The scaling coefficients quantify the contribution of speech and noise components, respectively, to the mixed speech-in-noise signal. For a given input signal, the resulting scaling coefficients $\psi_{\ell,k}$ and $\eta_{\ell,k}$ are obtained as the solution to the quadratic optimization problem with inequality constraints

$$(\psi_{\ell,k}, \eta_{\ell,k}) = \underset{(\psi, \eta)}{\operatorname{argmin}} \|\psi \mathbf{S}_{\ell,k} + \eta \mathbf{N}_{\ell,k} - \mathbf{X}_{\ell,k}\|_F^2 \quad (8)$$

subject to $0 \leq \psi \leq 1, \quad 0 \leq \eta \leq 1.$

The optimization problem is solved independently for each filter k and layer ℓ , and for each utterance in the dataset. An overview of the estimation procedure and its algorithmic formulation are shown in Fig. 2 and Algorithm 1.

Once the coefficients $\psi_{\ell,k}$ and $\eta_{\ell,k}$ have been estimated, they provide a quantitative basis for analyzing how speech and noise information is distributed across the network. At the layer level, coefficients can be aggregated across all filters and utterances to characterize global trends in speech or noise as a function

Figure 2: Schematic overview of the LENS method workflow. Three signals (mixture, clean, noise) are processed separately by the trained network. Corresponding feature maps at the layer and filter of interest are extracted from internal network activations. The constrained optimization problem (Eq. 8) is solved to obtain clean signal and noise (ψ, ν) weights. Cosine similarity values are computed for comparison.

of network depth. This aggregation enables a comparison of encoder and decoder behavior, as well as the identification of systematic changes in representation structure across layers.

At the channel level, coefficients are analyzed individually or averaged across utterances to assess the stability of feature-specific encoding for each filter. In the latter case, aggregation across utterances is performed by jointly considering all utterances within a single least-squares estimation. For example, filters with consistently high $\psi_{\ell,k}$ values and low $\eta_{\ell,k}$ values across utterances are considered speech-dominant, whereas filters exhibiting the opposite behavior are classified as noise-dominant. Filters for which neither coefficient consistently dominates are categorized as non-specific. This filter-wise analysis allows for a fine-grained characterization of internal representations and supports comparisons of filter specialization across layers.

2.3. Pseudo-SNR measure

The ratio of ψ to η can therefore be regarded as a proxy for a signal-to-noise ratio in feature space. Based on this, a pseudo-SNR (pSNR) metric is defined to quantify the relative speech-to-noise content of an utterance in the network’s internal representation for

layer ℓ and channel k as

$$\text{pSNR}_{\ell,k} = 20 \log_{10} \left(\frac{\psi_{\ell,k}}{\eta_{\ell,k}} \right). \quad (9)$$

This expression follows the same computation as the conventional SNR but operates on LENS weights ψ and η derived in feature-space rather than on speech and noise signals in the input domain. It retains interpretability akin to SNR while adapting it to the characterization of internal network representations obtained through non-linear processing. The resulting pSNR constitutes a continuous measure of the relative prominence of speech- versus noise-related features across layers and channels.

2.4. Cosine similarity measure

Cosine similarity constitutes a measure that is commonly used to quantify similarity between two vectors or matrices. It is defined for matrices \mathbf{X} and \mathbf{Y} as

$$\cos(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y}) = \frac{\langle \mathbf{X}, \mathbf{Y} \rangle_F}{\|\mathbf{X}\|_F \|\mathbf{Y}\|_F}, \quad (10)$$

where $\langle \cdot, \cdot \rangle_F$ denotes Frobenius inner product and $\|\cdot\|_F$ Frobenius norm. Cosine similarity is confined to the interval $[-1, 1]$, where a value of 1 denotes maximum similarity and 0 indicates orthogonality. The expected cosine similarity between two random matrices of size $m \times n$ is zero, with variance scaling as $\mathcal{O}(1/mn)$.

In the context of feature space representations of speech, noise and mixed signals, we consider cosine similarity as a baseline measure that we contrast to the LENS method. Cosine similarity of internal network representations obtained from a mixed speech-in-noise input signal, $\mathbf{X}_{\ell,k}$, to one obtained from the corresponding speech-only utterance, $\mathbf{S}_{\ell,k}$, is given by $\cos(\mathbf{X}_{\ell,k}, \mathbf{S}_{\ell,k})$. Similarly, $\cos(\mathbf{X}_{\ell,k}, \mathbf{N}_{\ell,k})$ denotes similarity to the noise-only representation. For example, units with a predominantly speech-component related representation are expected to result in a high value of $\cos(\mathbf{X}_{\ell,k}, \mathbf{S}_{\ell,k})$ and simultaneously a value of $\cos(\mathbf{X}_{\ell,k}, \mathbf{N}_{\ell,k})$ that should be close to zero.

3. Experiments and results

3.1. Signal processing parameters

We extract spectrogram representations of 16 kHz audio files with a fast Fourier transform with 512 bins, Hann window of length 25 ms and window shift 6.25 ms. The network input is fixed to 1618.75 milliseconds (256 time bins), resulting in a training batch input tensor of size (batch \times 2 \times 256 \times 256), with the dimensions being (batch \times channel \times time \times frequency) respectively. Time domain signals are reconstructed from the network’s output with inverse short-time Fourier transform and the overlap-add method. We generate 100 hours of anechoic training data using

the MS-DNS 2020 Challenge dataset [23]. Speech-in-noise mixtures are created with signal-to-noise ratios (SNRs) uniformly distributed between 0 dB and 20 dB, calculated relative to clean target speech. A separate 1-hour validation subset is generated to monitor model generalization and prevent overfitting during training. Noise types include a diverse range from real-world acoustic environments, including stationary noise from household appliances like vacuum cleaners and fans, as well as non-stationary noise such as construction sounds, fireworks, and door slams. Interferers with speech-like characteristics, including babble noise and background music, are included, but no interfering speakers. The U-Net architecture employed here, with its configuration shown in Fig. 1 and Tab. 1, was trained on the 100 hours audio data. Network analyses reported below require storage and analysis of feature maps from all channels and units of the network across all input utterances. To limit storage requirements, we randomly select 120 utterances from the validation set, ensuring that no two come from the same audio file, thus providing a representative sample for reliable assessment of the network’s response to speech and noise.

3.2. Quantitative layer analysis

To evaluate speech-selective filter behavior of the trained network, feature maps for all filters and layers are extracted using the same signal processing parameters as outlined above. The resulting representations are evaluated using the proposed LENS method and the cosine similarity measure. A global, layer-wise view of network representations is obtained by aggregating the measures for all feature maps across all layers and utterances. In this aggregation, each underlying data point corresponds to the response of a single channel to a single input utterance. Consequently, for a layer with K filters evaluated on 120 utterances, the resulting layer distribution contains $K \times 120$ data points, e.g., 64×120 for layer E1.

The plots in Fig. 3 show the distribution of speech- and noise-component selectivity, in terms of the LENS method’s ψ and η (top panel), and cosine similarities $\cos(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{S})$ and $\cos(\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{N})$ (bottom panel), respectively, across all layers. The vertical axis represents the encoder and decoder layers of the speech enhancement network. Each histogram, with applied kernel smoothing, depicts speech-related (blue) and noise-related (orange) coefficient values ranging from 0 to 1.

In the first encoder layer, the LENS coefficients ψ and η for speech and noise form broad, overlapping distributions, which corresponds well to the characteristics of the mixture signal. With increasing encoder depth, these distributions become progressively narrower. From layer E2 onward, a shift toward higher ψ values and lower η values becomes evident. In deeper layers such as EC1 and EC2, the distributions ap-

Figure 3: Layer-wise distribution of speech (blue) and noise (orange) channel responses across the network. The distributions indicate how strongly individual filters align with the speech or noise component based on LENS (top) and cosine similarity (bottom).

proach a near bi-modal structure, with most filters aligned toward speech features and only a small subset retaining notable noise contributions.

The cosine similarity shows a similar but less selective pattern overall. From layer E1 to E4, cosine similarity values increase for both speech and noise components, with the speech-related values forming a comparatively narrower distribution. In EC1 to EC3, the distribution of noise similarity becomes substantially wider. In particular, layers EC1 and EC2 show a wide distribution for noise similarity, while speech similarity remains consistently narrow. By layer EC3, the speech similarity is tightly clustered near the upper bound of 1, whereas in comparison the noise similarity remains dispersed, while also trending toward the upper bound.

In the decoder, the LENS coefficients begin in DC1 with both speech and noise distribution peaks near zero, indicating that most filters show only weak component weighting at this stage. In DC2 and DC3, the speech distribution quickly re-aligns toward the upper end at $\psi \approx 1$. From D1 onward, both noise and speech coefficient values become more broadly distributed. In D4, the speech distribution forms a narrow peak near one, whereas the noise distribution becomes slightly narrower around zero.

Cosine similarity values in the decoder exhibit a trend similar to those observed in the encoder. Layer DC1 shows high cosine similarity for both components, with distributions clustered toward the upper end of the scale, and moderate spread. In DC3, the noise distribution broadens while the speech peak remains concentrated. From D1 onward, both components gradually accumulate near the maximum value of 1, with the noise slightly spreading out in the last layer D4.

3.3. Qualitative analysis of feature maps

Figure 4 illustrates exemplary feature map responses from encoder layer E4 and decoder layer D4, selected to qualitatively compare cosine similarity with the LENS approach. The examples shown correspond to the filters with the highest speech-related score under the respective measure, allowing a direct inspection of how speech- and noise-related structure is reflected in feature maps.

Specifically, in encoder layer E4, filter 135 exhibits speech-specific behavior, with $\psi = 0.95$ and $\eta = 0.00$, alongside a high cosine similarity to clean speech (0.97). The corresponding feature map emphasizes time-frequency structures aligned with speech content while suppressing noise-related patterns. In contrast, filter 233 is selected based on a high cosine similarity to speech alone. Although it shows strong similarity to clean speech, it also exhibits a non-negligible similarity to noise (0.77), indicating a mixed response. This example highlights that cosine similarity alone may conflate speech and noise contributions, whereas

the LENS decomposition weights provide a clearer distinction between source-related components.

In the final decoder layer D4, we further investigate how well internal representations disentangle speech from noise by again selecting filters according to highest speech-related decomposition weight and cosine similarity. Filter 18, identified by its high speech attribution ($\psi = 0.97$), produces an activation that closely resembles the speech pattern while remaining nearly inactive for the noise signal ($\eta = 0.03$). This confirms that the decoder learns highly speech-selective units as it approaches the output. In contrast, filter 4, chosen based on having the highest cosine similarity for speech (0.99), exhibits also a high cosine similarity to noise (0.96), with speech- and noise-related activation visually being reflected in the mixed-signal feature map. This reiterates that cosine similarity alone cannot reliably distinguish between entangled and disentangled speech and noise representations. In contrast, the LENS decomposition directly quantifies the respective contributions of speech and noise, offering clearer interpretability of the mixture composition in the learned feature space.

3.4. Higher-layer feature maps based on LENS

Focusing on the proposed LENS approach, we qualitatively investigate examples of layers deeper in the network. In the initial convolutional layer (E1), weighting factors align closely with the mixture feature, with $\psi = 0.75$ and $\eta = 0.45$ indicating moderate presence of both clean and noise features, as can be seen in the presented feature maps. In layer E2, the mixture feature exhibits a strong speech component with some low frequency contribution as well as high frequency components, but weak noise activation, reflected by the weights $\psi = 0.91$ and $\eta = 0.12$. Layer E3 continues this trend, with a speech feature structure visually indistinguishable from the mixture feature, and low noise activation ($\psi = 0.89$, $\eta = 0.11$). Even at deeper layers such as EC2, despite the reduced spatial resolution, the mixture feature maintains localized alignment with the speech feature pattern, while the corresponding noise feature remains suppressed ($\psi = 0.99$, $\eta = 0.00$).

A similar pattern is observed in the decoder, where mixture features at each layer exhibit spatial correspondence to their clean and noise counterparts in alignment with the computed weights. In layer D4, the mixture and clean speech feature maps are nearly identical, while the noise feature is almost inactive, but slightly visible in the mixture with decomposition weights of $\psi = 0.98$ and $\eta = 0.29$. In layer D3, the mixture feature continues to reflect the structure of the clean input, with moderate residual noise presence, indicated by $\psi = 0.75$ and $\eta = 0.25$. In D2, the mixture and clean speech map share more similarities with $\psi = 0.81$ and $\eta = 0.17$. The deepest decoder layer shown here, DC2, has a coarse resolution, but,

Figure 4: Layers E4 and D4 with filters selected by their highest ranking ψ -values, and highest cosine similarity for comparison.

similar to the encoder, yields highly speech-dominant weights at $\psi = 0.97$ with $\eta = 0.00$, which correspond well to their visualized patterns.

3.5. Distribution of feature maps

To characterize how filters are distributed with respect to speech and noise dominance, we consider the categorization of channels based on the discriminative weights ψ and η . Each channel is assigned to one of three categories: speech-specific, noise-specific, or non-specific. Specifically, categories are based on empirically determined thresholds for speech-specificity if $\psi \geq 0.7$ and $\eta \leq 0.3$, noise-specificity if $\eta \geq 0.7$ and $\psi \leq 0.3$, and non-specific otherwise.

Figure 6 summarizes the resulting distributions using two complementary aggregation strategies. In Fig. 6a, absolute counts are shown per layer, where each underlying data point corresponds to one filter-utterance pair. Consequently, the total number of counts per layer scales with both the number of channels and the number of utterances. Across encoder and decoder, the relative proportions of speech-specific, non-specific, and noise-specific filter-utterance pairs are largely consistent. In all layers, speech-specific units form the dominant category, followed by non-specific units, while noise-specific units remain comparatively few. This overall pattern is preserved across the encoder-decoder architecture, with minor variations observed before and after the latent space in layers EC3 and DC1, where the number of noise-specific categorizations increases slightly.

In contrast, Fig. 6b shows filter counts averaged across utterances, such that each filter contributes a single (utterance-independent) data point per layer. This representation reflects how consistently individual units are categorized across different input utterances. Across the encoder, filters in Fig. 6b reflect a predominance of nonspecific channels in the early layers, followed by an increasing number of speech-specific categorizations toward deeper encoder layers. In the decoder, the total number of speech-specific channels decreases in the layers immediately following the latent representation and slightly increases again toward the output layers. Compared to the utterance-dependent view in Fig. 6a, this representation emphasizes the overall lower degree of categorization-consistency when each channel is assigned to a single category for the entire validation dataset in an utterance-independent manner.

3.6. pSNR Differences

To analyze filter behavior across the network in terms of the pseudo-SNR (pSNR, Eq. 9), we apply the same two complementary aggregation strategies introduced in Section 3.5.

In the first approach, pSNR values are derived from all $(\psi_{\ell,k}, \eta_{\ell,k})$ -pairs for each utterance and are

Figure 5: Encoder and decoder feature maps for a subset of layers with corresponding mixture weight values ψ and η .

aggregated per-layer across all channels and utterances, with each channel–utterance combination contributing one underlying data point. The resulting distributions, shown in Fig. 7a for channels categorized as speech-selective, provide a global view of pSNR values across network layers for speech-dominant channels. Across the encoder, the pSNR distributions shift toward higher values with increasing depth, as reflected by a rising median and upper quartiles. Around the bottleneck, this trend saturates, followed by increased spread and less consistent median behavior in the decoder layers. Overall, the encoder exhibits a more structured progression of pSNR values, whereas the decoder shows greater variability across layers.

Figure 7b shows the pSNR distributions for filters categorized as noise-dominant. Across all layers, pSNR values are predominantly negative. In the encoder, the distributions exhibit relatively stable medians and interquartile ranges across depth. Around the bottleneck and throughout the decoder, the distributions show increased spread, with a varying median deeper in the decoder.

The second analysis approach examines filter stability by comparing average pSNR values for each unit across the validation set. Here, pSNR is computed from $(\psi_{\ell,k}, \eta_{\ell,k})$ values derived from the constrained optimization (Eq. 8) carried out over all utterances in the validation set. Thus, each channel contributes one underlying pSNR data point. This aggregation reflects the average relative response of the filter to speech throughout the dataset, in anal-

ogy to the analysis carried out for Fig. 6b above. Figure 7c shows the resulting layer-wise distributions of the average pSNR values for filters categorized as speech-dominant. In early encoder layers, the distributions are narrow, indicating limited spread of averaged pSNR values across filters. With increasing depth in the encoder, median values increase and distributions broaden toward the deeper layers. In the decoder, the distributions show increasing median and overall comparably small spread, with the exception of layer D4 close to the output, where an increased spread is observed.

3.7. Exemplary filter behavior across utterances

To further explore the utterance-specific response properties of network units, as implied by the analyses in the preceding sections, we here provide a detailed example of a single unit, filter-channel 44 in layer E3. This permits, even if somewhat anecdotal, an analysis of whether a given unit consistently responds to either speech or noise patterns across varying inputs. Fig. 8 illustrates the progression of decomposition weights across utterances in this filter. Results show that some utterances yield high ψ with low η values, while others produce the opposite pattern. The two measures are approximately inversely correlated across all samples, as expected from the linear decomposition constraint, with no cases exhibiting simultaneously high values for both weights. The unit shown responds in a highly speech-specific manner to some audio inputs, e.g., utterance 20 from the sampled validation set results in $\psi = 1.00$ and $\eta = 0.00$. For other inputs,

(a) Absolute counts per layer across utterances.

(b) Filters averaged across utterances.

Figure 6: Distribution of channels classified by $\psi \geq 0.7$ & $\eta \leq 0.3$ as speech, $\eta \geq 0.7$ & $\psi \leq 0.3$ as noise, and nonspecific in-between. (a) shows total counts per layer for all utterances. For example, layer E1 has $64 \times 120 = 7680$ counts in total. (b) shows the filters of every layer averaged across utterances, e.g., layer E1 has 64 filters for 64 data points shown here.

e.g., utterance 83, it responds with a tendency toward noise-specific characteristics, with values of $\psi = 0.33$ and $\eta = 0.69$.

4. Discussion

4.1. LENS, cosine similarity, and network representations

The feature map analyses across the encoder and decoder provide a global, layer-wise view of how individual filters relate to speech and noise components, using the (ψ, η) LENS decomposition and cosine similarity as proxy measures. By aggregating filter responses across utterances and filters within each layer (e.g., Fig. 3), these measures characterize systematic trends in network representations rather than the behavior of individual feature maps in isolation. They do not aim to establish fully disentangled features, but instead indicate whether filters, on average, consistently align with specific acoustic patterns, such as speech-dominant or noise-dominant characteristics.

The observed behavior of LENS decomposition and cosine similarity across the network yields a coherent picture of how filter populations evolve with depth. At the layer level, the emergence of bi-modal or skewed distributions in the decomposition weights ψ and η suggests that many filters collectively develop consistent alignment with either speech or noise characteristics across different utterances. These global tendencies are partially reflected by cosine similarity, which often highlights strong alignment but lacks selectivity, frequently producing high correlation values for both speech and noise components. In particular, deeper encoder layers exhibit elevated cosine similarity with both inputs, emphasizing that cosine similarity captures overall alignment strength but provides limited discrimination between competing sources at the layer level.

As a consequence, cosine similarity does not offer an equally informative representation of filter special-

ization when interpreted in an aggregated, layer-wise manner. While high cosine similarity values indicate strong correspondence between feature maps, they do not reliably distinguish whether this correspondence arises from speech or noise components. In contrast, the LENS decomposition enables a clearer separation through the relative magnitudes of ψ and η , allowing filters to be categorized unambiguously as speech-dominant, noise-dominant, or non-specific. This distinction becomes particularly apparent in deeper layers, where aggregated cosine similarity remains high, whereas the LENS weights reveal more differentiated source-specific structure.

4.2. Pseudo-SNR and filter categorization

The pseudo-SNR is introduced as a proxy for characterizing filter behavior in terms of relative speech and noise contributions. In contrast to the categorical filter distributions shown in Fig. 6, which summarize the prevalence of speech-, noise-, and non-specific filters, the pseudo-SNR provides a continuous measure that captures the strength and stability of individual filters. Together, these views enable a more differentiated analysis of network representations, combining information about how many filters fall into a given category with how consistently and strongly these tendencies are expressed.

At a global level, the layer-wise pSNR distributions in Fig. 7 complement the filter statistics in Fig. 6. While Fig. 6a indicates that the relative proportions of speech-, non-specific, and noise-specific filter-utterance pairs remain largely consistent across the encoder and decoder, Fig. 7 reveals how the degree of speech or noise classification varies across layers. In particular, the encoder exhibits a systematic shift in the pSNR distributions toward higher values, whereas the decoder shows increased variability, with broader distributions and less pronounced layer-wise trends. This suggests that, although the overall number of classified filters remains similar, the strength with which

(a) pSNR values for each speech specific filter-utterance pair.

(b) pSNR values for each noise specific filter-utterance pair.

(c) Speech filters averaged across utterances.

Figure 7: Distribution of pSNR values for speech filters classified by $\psi \geq 0.7$ & $\eta \leq 0.3$ as speech. (a) Shows pSNR for each filter-utterance pair classified as speech across all utterances, (b) Shows pSNR for each filter-utterance pair classified as noise across all utterances (c) Shows the average pSNR for all filters classified as speech in every layer, when averaged across utterances.

individual filters align with speech or noise changes across network depth.

The filter-averaged view in Fig. 6b further highlights that many filters do not behave uniformly across utterances, motivating the use of aggregated pSNR statistics. As shown in Fig. 7c, averaging pSNR values per filter reveals that some filters exhibit stable speech-dominant behavior, while others remain closer to zero, indicating mixed or non-specific responses. These observations suggest that filter specialization is not necessarily absolute, but instead reflects varying degrees of consistency across inputs. Filters with intermediate or variable pSNR values may capture acoustic structures that are shared between speech and noise, such as temporal dynamics or spectral transitions, rather than source-exclusive features.

4.3. Model design implications

Pseudo-SNR and filter activation analyses provide insight into how architectural components influence

Figure 8: (Top) Input mixture and noise spectra for utterances 20 and 83. (Bottom) Distribution of ψ and η across all 120 utterances for filter 44 in encoder layer E3.

the propagation of speech- and noise-related information within the network. In particular, the observed filter behavior in the decoder suggests that lateral connections from the encoder contribute not only high-resolution structure, but also residual noise-features. This is reflected in a reduction of pSNR values for speech-specific filters across a range of decoder layers, as shown in Fig. 7.

From a design perspective, these observations suggest that the role of lateral connections warrants careful consideration in speech enhancement architectures. While skip connections are essential for preserving fine-grained temporal and spectral detail, the propagation of features with reduced speech selectivity into later stages of the network may be detrimental to noise suppression. Mechanisms that modulate the contribution of skip-connected features have been explored in prior work with some success [24, 25]. In light of the observed reduction in speech selectivity at later decoder stages, such approaches may represent a relevant direction to consider in future speech enhancement architectures, particularly in scenarios requiring strong noise suppression.

In addition, the re-emergence of speech-aligned filters toward the final decoder layers, as reflected in the pSNR distributions, points to the importance of late-stage refinement during signal reconstruction. This suggests that decoder capacity and depth play a role in consolidating speech-specific features prior to output generation, and that architectural choices affecting this stage may influence the balance between detail preservation and noise suppression.

Finally, the filter-level analyses indicate that a subset of filters respond to acoustic patterns that are not exclusive to speech or noise, such as transient events or stationary low-frequency structures. These responses, observed across multiple encoder layers, suggest that the network implicitly develops partial specialization for shared acoustic features. Related observations have been reported in prior work [26], indicating that deep audio models tend to discriminate signals using combinations of basic acoustic features rather than relying on high-level, source-specific concepts. Rather than enforcing a strict speech-noise separation at the level of individual filters, these findings suggest that future architectural designs may benefit from acknowledging the role of shared acoustic representations. For example, architectural biases or training objectives that encourage sensitivity to specific acoustic pattern classes could complement regression-based enhancement, potentially improving both interpretability and robustness without requiring some form of disentanglement.

5. Conclusion and Outlook

This work introduced a framework for analyzing internal representations in a speech enhancement network by examining feature map activations and their

relative contributions from speech and noise inputs. A linear decomposition method (LENS) was proposed, in which each feature map is approximated as a weighted combination of activations obtained from clean speech and noise signals. The resulting coefficients, ψ and η , provide an interpretable, component-based description of filter behavior and form the basis for categorizing filters as speech-specific, noise-specific, or non-specific.

Compared to cosine similarity, which measures alignment in feature space, the proposed LENS framework offers a more informative characterization of activation composition. While cosine similarity often indicates strong correspondence with both speech and noise inputs simultaneously, the decomposition weights directly quantify the relative presence of each component. Building on this formulation, a pseudo signal-to-noise ratio (pSNR) was introduced as a compact, log-scaled proxy for representation of speech-related information at the feature map level. The pSNR enables quantitative comparisons of filter behavior across layers and aggregation levels, revealing systematic trends across the encoder-decoder architecture, including increasing speech alignment in deeper encoder layers, mixed distributions around the latent representation, and renewed speech dominance toward the final decoder stage. At the same time, filter-averaged analyses indicate that many filters exhibit non-specific behavior across utterances, suggesting sensitivity to shared acoustic patterns rather than exclusive source representations.

Beyond characterization, the proposed methodology provides a means to examine how architectural components influence internal representations. In particular, the observed reduction in speech selectivity in decoder layers following the latent representation highlights the role of the U-Net’s lateral connections in shaping reconstruction behavior. While these connections are essential for preserving fine-grained structure, they may also propagate representations with reduced speech selectivity, potentially limiting the effectiveness of late-stage noise suppression. The interaction between lateral feature propagation and source-selective representations therefore warrants further investigation.

Overall, this work presents a methodology for interpreting deep speech enhancement models based on activation decomposition, establishes pseudo-SNR as a useful metric for filter-level analysis, and demonstrates how population-level trends can be observed across the model architecture’s extent. Future work may explore more refined categorization of filters based on acoustic pattern classes, investigate training-time constraints and inductive biases that align network representations with known signal characteristics, with the goal of improving interpretability and robustness without enforcing strict source disentanglement.

Acknowledgements

This work was funded by the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (DFG, German Research Foundation) under project ID 352015383 (SFB 1330/B3).

References

- [1] M. Sundararajan, A. Taly, Q. Yan, Axiomatic attribution for deep networks, in: International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML), PMLR, 2017, pp. 3319–3328.
- [2] J. T. Springenberg, A. Dosovitskiy, T. Brox, M. Riedmiller, Striving for Simplicity: The All Convolutional Net, in: International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR) Workshop, 2015.
- [3] K. Simonyan, A. Vedaldi, A. Zisserman, Deep Inside Convolutional Networks: Visualising Image Classification Models and Saliency Maps, in: International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR) Workshop, 2014.
- [4] R. R. Selvaraju, M. Cogswell, A. Das, R. Vedantam, D. Parikh, D. Batra, Grad-CAM: Visual Explanations from Deep Networks via Gradient-Based Localization, in: IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV), 2017, pp. 618–626.
- [5] J. Yosinski, J. Clune, A. M. Nguyen, T. J. Fuchs, H. Lipson, Understanding Neural Networks Through Deep Visualization, International Conference of Deep Learning (ICML): Deep Learning Workshop. (2015).
- [6] G. Montavon, A. Binder, S. Lapuschkin, W. Samek, K.-R. Müller, Layer-Wise Relevance Propagation: An Overview, Springer International Publishing, Cham, 2019, pp. 193–209.
- [7] A. Shrikumar, P. Greenside, A. Kundaje, Learning Important Features Through Propagating Activation Differences, in: D. Precup, Y. W. Teh (Eds.), Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning, Vol. 70 of Proceedings of Machine Learning Research, PMLR, 2017, pp. 3145–3153.
- [8] D. Erhan, Y. Bengio, A. Courville, P. Vincent, Visualizing Higher-Layer Features of a Deep Network, Technical Report, Université de Montréal (01 2009).
- [9] M. T. Ribeiro, S. Singh, C. Guestrin, Why Should I Trust You?: Explaining the Predictions of Any Classifier., in: HLT-NAACL Demos, The Association for Computational Linguistics, 2016, pp. 97–101.
- [10] S. M. Lundberg, S.-I. Lee, A unified approach to interpreting model predictions, in: Advances in Neural Information Processing Systems (NeurIPS), Vol. 30, Curran Associates, Inc., 2017.
- [11] Sören Becker and Johanna Vielhaben and Marcel Ackermann and Klaus-Robert Müller and Sebastian Lapuschkin and Wojciech Samek, Audiomnist: Exploring explainable artificial intelligence for audio analysis on a simple benchmark, Journal of the Franklin Institute 361 (1) (2024) 418–428.
- [12] V. Haunschmid, E. Manilow, G. Widmer, audioLIME: Listenable Explanations Using Source Separation, 13th International Workshop on Machine Learning and Music (2020).
- [13] S. Sivasankaran, E. Vincent, D. Fohr, Explaining Deep Learning Models for Speech Enhancement, in: Interspeech, 2021, pp. 696–700.
- [14] P. Agrawal, S. Ganapathy, Interpretable Representation Learning for Speech and Audio Signals Based on Relevance Weighting, IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing 28 (2020) 2823–2836.
- [15] F. Mathieu, T. Courtat, G. Richard, G. Peeters, Learning Interpretable Filters In Wav-UNet For Speech Enhancement, in: ICASSP 2023 - 2023 IEEE International Conference on Acoustics, Speech and Signal Processing (ICASSP), 2023, pp. 1–5.
- [16] S. I. Mimilakis, K. Drossos, G. Schuller, Unsupervised Interpretable Representation Learning for Singing Voice Separation, in: 2020 28th European Signal Processing Conference (EUSIPCO), 2021, pp. 1412–1416.
- [17] N. Das, J. Zegers, H. Van hamme, T. Francart, A. Bertrand, Linear versus deep learning methods for noisy speech separation for EEG-informed attention decoding, Journal of Neural Engineering 17 (4) (2020) 046039.
- [18] E. J. Nustede, J. Anemüller, On the Generalization Ability of Complex-Valued Variational U-Networks for Single-Channel Speech Enhancement, IEEE/ACM Transactions on Audio, Speech, and Language Processing 32 (2024) 3838–3849.
- [19] H.-S. Choi, J. Kim, J. Huh, A. Kim, J.-W. Ha, K. Lee, Phase-Aware Speech Enhancement with Deep Complex U-Net, in: International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR), 2019.
- [20] F. Chollet, Xception: Deep learning with depthwise separable convolutions, in: IEEE Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference (CVPR), 2017, pp. 1800–1807.
- [21] I. Higgins, L. Matthey, A. Pal, C. P. Burgess, X. Glorot, M. M. Botvinick, S. Mohamed, A. Lerchner, beta-VAE: Learning Basic Visual Concepts with a Constrained Variational Framework, in: International Conference on Learning Representations (ICLR), 2017.
- [22] K. He, X. Zhang, S. Ren, J. Sun, Delving Deep into Rectifiers: Surpassing Human-Level Performance on ImageNet Classification, in: Proceedings of the IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV), 2015, pp. 1026–1034.
- [23] C. K. Reddy, V. Gopal, R. Cutler, E. Beyrami, R. Cheng, H. Dubey, S. Matusevych, R. Aichner, A. Aazami, S. Braun, et al., The Interspeech 2020 Deep Noise Suppression Challenge: Datasets, Subjective Testing Framework, and Challenge Results, in: Interspeech 2020, 2020.
- [24] F. Deng, T. Jiang, X.-R. Wang, C. Zhang, Y. Li, NAAGN: Noise-Aware Attention-Gated Network for Speech Enhancement, in: Interspeech, 2020, pp. 2457–2461.
- [25] Seorim Hwang and Sung Wook Park and Youngcheol Park, Monoaural Speech Enhancement Using a Nested U-Net with Two-Level Skip Connections, in: Interspeech, 2022, pp. 191–195.
- [26] T.-Y. Wu, Y.-X. Lin, T.-W. Weng, AND: Audio Network Dissection for Interpreting Deep Acoustic Models, in: Proceedings of the International Conference on Machine Learning (ICML), 2024.